

Public Debt and Economic Growth in Nigeria: Decades of Unending Struggle

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Abstract

This paper examines the role of public debt in Nigeria's economic growth process from 1981 to 2021. Generally, economies resort to debt financing in economic growth to lessen tax burden on the production chain. Applying autoregressive distributed lag models on annualized country data set, we showed that public debt positively affects economic growth in Nigeria. Total public debt in Nigeria could thus be positive and record nearly 63% increase to economic growth in the long run. Most of the negative effects of public debt on economic growth reveal that debt servicing is still unsustainable to the Nigerian sub-region. Thus, we argued that deliberate policies be put in place to ensure that the accumulation of debt in Nigeria is consistent with the country's growth objectives. Furthermore, government is encouraged to put in place, fiscal reforms that would help in the better management of domestic debt and the acceleration of economic growth in years following this study.

Key words: Public debt, External debt, Domestic debt, Nigeria, Growth.

JEL Classification: C52, E12, H63, O41, O47.

1.0 Background to the Study

Globally, financing government's budget requires a sustainable funding policy to stimulate economic growth. When tax revenues fall short of expenditure estimate of the government, other options are usually explored either to increase tax or borrow internally or externally (Owusu-Nantwi and Erickson, 2016). When government resorts to borrowing which is the alternative way of avoiding tax burdens, it leads to public debt (Ogunmuyiwa, 2010). Public debts are therefore, both short-term and long-term loans sourced by government to finance public expenditures as a result of inadequate public revenues. To respond to the global economic recessions after the Second World War many economies (developed and developing) resorted to borrowing either domestically

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or externally to fund budget deficits. These strives had led to the accumulation of public debt resulting in the economic recession and debt crisis in the early 2000s by many developed and developing countries (Donayre and Taivan, 2017).

Adom (2016) opined that it is highly impracticable for a country to run a surplus budget, and therefore, the acquisition of public debt becomes inevitable. It follows that the acquisition of public debts is not really a problem; nevertheless, building up public debt to unsustainable levels can stifle economic growth (Adom, 2016). For instance, available literature submits that unsustainable public debt reduces a country's competitiveness and increases a country's financial market susceptibility to international shock, which consequently impedes economic growth (Cochrane, 2011; Castro, Felix, Juho and Maria, 2015). It also implies that, even though borrowing to finance public spending is not bad, it equally has an adverse effect on economic growth if not managed efficiently and effectively. For example, the global debt crisis experienced in the mid-1970s and 1980s was attributed to poor-debt management policies between low- and middle-income countries (Marquez, 2000). Debt acquisition in these periods was very high, and the servicing of debt became the core challenge for the emerging and less advanced economies because of the increase in short term loans to finance long term projects without a corresponding ability to fulfill debt obligations on time (Marquez, 2000).

The oil crisis also adversely affected economic development because developing economies strived to sustain growth rates and borrowed heavily so as to complete development projects (Stambuli, 1998). At that time, the allocation for most of the projects by governments was mismatched with the financing maturity structure where authorities take short-term loans and invest heavily in long-term projects, thereby making it difficult to retrieve these funds to settle their debt obligation (Krumm, 1985). During this period, most African governments that had never borrowed before took advantage of the Euro-markets platform to borrow huge amounts to finance their budget (Krumm, 1985). In spite of the imminent debt crisis, advanced economies were dreadfully willing to settle long-term credits of developing economies with shorter maturities, resulting in the increased debt level of developing countries from \$130bn in 1973 to about \$612 bn in 1984 (IMF, 1984).

Less developed economies (LDCs), characterized by low capital formation owing to low levels of domestic savings and investment, pursued policies aimed at

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attaining a sustainable economy (Adepoju, Salau and Obayelu, 2007). It was expected that these LDCs, when faced with a paucity of funds, would resort to borrowing from external sources so as to supplement domestic savings (Aluko and Arowolo, 2010). Soludo (2003) asserted that countries borrow for two broad reasons: macroeconomic reasons to finance higher levels of investment and consumption (or to finance transitory balance of payments deficits and avoid budget constraints). This implies that the economy indulges in debt to boost economic growth and reduce poverty. He was also of the opinion that once an initial stock of debt grows to a certain threshold, servicing then becomes a burden, and countries find themselves on the wrong side of the debt – Laffer curve with debt crowding out investment and growth. This seems to be the position of Nigeria today because investment, which will accordingly result in high-speed growth with a positive effect on poverty, is moving sporadically in both positive and negative directions. The constant need for governments to borrow in order to finance budget deficits has led to the creation of external debt (Osinubi and Olaleru, 2006). Public debt constitutes a medium used by countries to bridge their deficit gap and carry out economic projects that are able to increase the standard of living of the citizenry and promote sustainable growth and development. Hakeem and Bolade (2015) stated that public borrowing ought to accelerate economic growth, especially when domestic financing is inadequate. Public debt also improves total factor productivity through an increase in output, which in turn enhances Gross Domestic Product (GDP) growth of a nation. Therefore, the importance of public debt cannot be overemphasized as it is an ardent booster of growth, improving living standards and alleviating poverty.

THEORETICAL LITERATURE

2.2.1 Keynesian Theory of Public Debt

The Keynesian economists maintained that fiscal expansion have the proclivity to increase aggregate demand for private sector goods through the fiscal multiplier, thereby stimulating the growth of private investment (Gordon and Cosimo, 2018).

The economic disaster shaped by the Great Depression of the 1930s was in part responsible for the growth of the modern theory of public debt. The conventional view that steady unbalanced budgets and fast-increasing public debt impaired the financial stability of the nations slowly gave way to Keynesian ideology. Keynes (1936) stated

that a large public debt is a national asset rather than a liability and that steady deficit spending is necessary for the economic progress of the countries.

Keynes attacked the view of the classical that the economy tends to equilibrium at full employment. He argued that if there were unemployed resources, which the private sector could not employ, the resources could be put to use by the unbalanced budget. He was of the view that an increase in public debt through the multiplier effects would raise the national income. He associated public borrowing with deficit financing and agreed that the government should borrow for all purposes so that effective demand in the economy is increased, which would result in increased employment and output. He did not differentiate between productive and unproductive expenditure as the classical. Keynes stated that borrowing for consumption was as important as borrowing for investment in productive goods because consumption expenditure induced investment to rise up.

2.2.4 The Ricardo Hypothesis of Public Debt

This theory of public debt was propounded by David Ricardo in 1819. In his principles, Ricardo developed the theory of public debts by stating that the ordinary and extraordinary spending of government were mainly payments made to sustain unproductive labourers. Therefore, any saving from the government expenses would be included in the income if not to the capital of the contributors. Ricardo, in a letter written to McCullochin in 1816, believed that public expenditure was wasteful ventures undertaken by the state. Ricardo's theory of public debt was then based on the fact that the primary burden to the community was derived from the wasteful nature of public expenditure itself rather than from the methods adopted to finance such expenditure (Precious, 2015). The theory postulated that financing public expenditure should be focused on drawing the funds from the liquid resources of the community. This is because, to focus on the economy, it does not make any significant difference whether the funds were raised by loan or taxes. Accordingly, Ricardo's argument about payment of interest on public debt deals with a transfer of wealth from one pocket to another within the society. Thus, when countries borrow, it is uncertain whether the loan would be used productively or unproductively. If the loan is used productively, it leads to growth, but if it is used unproductively, it deters economic growth in the economy (Okoye, Modebe, Erin and Evbuomwan, 2013). In conclusion, this theory is relevant to

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the study, as it would help determine whether, actually, the government expenditure in Nigeria has over time been used productively or unproductively according to the theory.

2.2.5 Two-Gap Growth Model

These are contained in the post-Keynesian growth models for closed economies as designed by Harrod (1939) and Domar (1946). They tried to identify the preconditions for the economic growth of market economies. These two preconditions are essentially rooted in the Nigerian economy, and these are (i) Internally, inadequate savings would definitely translate to low investment. The gap between these two is called saving constraints (saving gap). Closing this gap requires foreign direct investment (FDI). (ii) Externally, inadequate foreign exchange arising from inability to export vis-avis high importation will lead to a shortfall in foreign exchange. The GAP between this duo is called foreign exchange constraints (TRADE GAP), which can be corrected by foreign aid.

When external finance – either grants or loans – supplements domestic resources, then we have “the two-gap model”. The major assumption of this model is that most developing countries either face a shortage of domestic savings to augment investment opportunities, or they (developed countries) are faced with foreign exchange constraints to finance the needed capital and intermediate goods. In their book, *Economic Development*, Todaro and Smith (2004) claimed that most two-gap models assume that the savings gap and the foreign exchange gap are unequal in magnitude and independent in nature. The implication of this is that one of the two gaps would be “binding” or “dominant” for any less developed country at any point in time. Essentially, the two-gap model is based on the gap between a country's own provision of resources and its absorptive capacity. These two gaps are known as the savings gap, where savings fall short of what can be effectively and productively invested, and the foreign exchange gap, where earnings of foreign exchange fall short of the amount needed to purchase the necessary foreign materials, components, etc. Whichever of the two gaps is binding (or is the greatest) will constrain the amount of investment and capital formation that can be undertaken.

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Derivation of the Two Gap Model:

We start with the basic macroeconomic identity where:

Aggregate output = aggregate expenditure as represented by Equation 2.1 as follows:

$$Y = C + I + (X - M) \quad \text{Equation 2.1}$$

where: C = consumption; I = investment (or domestic capital formation); x = exports; M = imports.

Now, sources of resources used in the economy = uses of resources in the economy: expenditure targets as shown by Equation 2.2 as:

$$Y + M = C + I + X \quad \text{Equation 2.2}$$

Subtracting C from both sides, we get Equation 2.3 as:

$$Y - C + M = I + X \quad \text{Equation 2.3}$$

Then Equation 2.4 is represented as:

$$S + M = I + X \quad \text{Equation 2.4}$$

The relationship can be restated as follows:

$$\begin{array}{ccc} M - X & = & I - S \\ \text{Foreign Exchange Gap} & & \text{Saving Gap} \end{array}$$

The two constitute two separate constraints. Eliminating one does not get rid of the other.

Note: The analysis rests on the premise that domestic investment can be financed by domestic saving as well as through inflows of capital.

2.2.6 The Harrod-Domar Growth Model

Harrod independently discovered this idea in 1939, and Domar developed it in 1946. The Harrod-Domar growth model establishes a clear link between savings and economic growth. According to the idea, an economy's growth rate is determined by the amount of national saving and the productivity of capital investment. As a result, a rise in the savings rate and the marginal productivity of capital will result in an increase in the rate of production growth. According to the model, economic growth is dependent on

policies that enhance investment by boosting saving and utilizing that investment more effectively through technical development (Harrod, 1939 and Domar, 1946).

Although the Harrod-Domar model was used to explain the source of economic growth, the theory has also been adopted to explain the effect of debt on economic growth in developing countries. This is because labour is plentiful in such nations, but physical capital is scarce, resulting in slower economic advancement. Furthermore, developing nations lack adequate per capita income to encourage high rates of savings, resulting in inadequate capital stock building through investment. External borrowing is viewed as capital that helps to cover the funding gap in emerging nations in order to boost growth (Eaton, 1993).

2.2.7 The Endogenous Growth Theory

The endogenous growth theory was propounded by one of the neoclassical scholars of solo-swan growth and a Nobel Prize-winning economist, Robert Solo, in the year 1957 (Alejandro and Ileana, 2017). The theory suggests that economic growth is appropriately related to externally generated revenue but internally generated variables in fixed capital formations, investments in infrastructures and internally generated economic drivers in a particular economy, through endogenous variables and not exogenous factors (Alejandro and Ileana, 2017). The endogenous growth theory is in contradiction with the classical growth model, which postulates exogenous growth, asserting that growth factors such as technological innovation are the main source of economic growth. By economic implications, endogenous growth theory posited that government policies have significant roles to play in economic growth if the government policies are directed towards infrastructural development that is capable of stimulating growth toward market competitive advantages and innovation in the production of domestic products, and services (Anome, Bandiera, and Presbitero, 2015; and Ewaida, 2017).

One of the key implications of endogenous growth theory includes increasing returns to scale from capital investments in the enhancement of industrial sectors, education, health care, telecommunication, and other infrastructure that can improve indigenous growth. Issues of investment in internally generated research and development are also considered major sources of technological progress for any given economy. Some of the assumptions of the theory are that an investment in human capital

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projects without a corresponding investment in human capital will lead to disequilibrium and not have endearing and enduring growth in the economy of a nation but could reflect on the growth of the economy on a temporary basis, leading to a short-lived expected growth. In addition, the endogenous theory hypothesis is that a sustainable and enduring investment and increase in capital investment can improve a nation's economy (Essien, Agboegbulem, Mba and Onamonu, 2016).

CONCEPTUAL

2.1.1 The Concept of Public Debt

Public debt, also known as national debt or sovereign debt, is the aggregate amount of money the government owes to their citizens and/or local financial organisations (domestic debt) or foreign financial organisations (external debt). Similarly, Makau (2008) opined that public debt is the total amount of borrowing in a country that is owed to lenders within and outside the country. It is made up of money within individuals, institutions, banks and non-bank financial institutions (NBFI) and outside the country from individuals and government institutions – bilateral and multilateral. Nnamocha (2002) defined public debts as the debt of the public sector. According to him, it is the indebtedness of the government and the obligations of the government to other individuals and institutions in and outside the country. Today, public debt is more or less a fiscal policy instrument of government, as the government uses it to augment her income and expenditure framework and to balance deficit budgets. If the debt is internal, it means that the country owes itself. In that case, when interest and principal are paid, income is transferred from one citizen to another. The burden becomes pronounced when the poor are taxed to pay the rich, who are the beneficiaries of these treasury bills, stocks and bonds. If, on the other hand, the debt is external, it means that the country is owing citizens and institutions of other countries, in which case interest and principal paid constitute capital flight as it is paid to other countries in foreign denominations and through export. Public debt could also mean the portion of total debt which has a direct charge on government revenues as well as the debt obtained from the IMF (Nnamocha, 2002).

Christabell (2013) postulated that public debt constitutes one of the major indicators of the macroeconomic variables which reflect the image of countries in the international markets. Generally, it is one of the determinants of foreign direct

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investment flows. Prudent management of public debt increases economic growth and stability via resource mobilisation with low borrowing costs and limited financial risk exposure (Christabell, 2013).

Public debt can also be described as the total debts of a country, which includes debts of governments at all levels, such as local, state and national governments, thereby showing how many public expenditures are financed through borrowing instead of taxation (Makau, 2008 cited in Christabell, 2013). Public debt is one of the approaches used in financing government projects, even though the approach is not the only way. The government can change its operations, as she can also create money to monetize its debts, and by creating money to finance government operations, the need to pay interest may be removed (Makau, 2008). According to Kibul (1997), the fundamental factor that causes public debt to rise is over-reliance on external borrowing (as is the case in Nigeria) to augment capital formation in the nation's economy. If the interest payment is high, the deficit on the current account will also be high, thereby resulting in the huge debt burden.

Akos and Isvan (2019) defined public debt burden as the overall long term impact of debt which eventually lowers consumption and reduces economic welfare, as each generation burdens the next by leaving behind a smaller aggregate stock of capital. Obadan (2004) opined that Nigeria started experiencing a public debt burden from the early 1980s due to falling oil prices in the international market, which caused a reduction in foreign exchange earnings. The increase in Nigeria's loans and advances from the international capital market and multilateral institutions, the increase in backlogged foreign trade arrears, the defaulting charge on overdue loans, recapitalization of outstanding interest liabilities, as well as the depreciation of the naira, jointly increased the volume of Nigeria's external debt burden over the years (Obadan, 2004).

Debt burden is measured by total debt-to-GDP ratio (Debt overhang). Debt overhang arises when debt stock exceeds government's ability to repay. This leads to an increase in taxes towards generating adequate revenue to settle both foreign and domestic creditors, thus discouraging investments due to a sudden increase in taxes (Abdullahi *et al.*, 2016). This implies that accumulation of debt hampers economic prosperity through tax disincentive. Tax disincentive denotes that rising debt stock impede investment as potential investors foresee a possible tax increase on future income in a bid to repay the borrowed funds. As such, the debt overhang theory

recommends that borrowed funds be well invested in productive sectors capable of generating adequate revenue for repaying the debt and financing domestic investment (Were, 2001).

Isaac and Rosa (2016) also postulated that sub-national governments acquire debt mainly to finance public investment projects that complement the private investments to translate into improved economic growth, from which the economy becomes sustainable and has no risk for their finances. Nassir and Wani (2016) opined that a debt implies an obligation to pay money, deliver goods, or render service under an express or implied agreement. Hence, they described public debt as the total debts of the nation, which include the debt of national, state and local governments that revealed how much public spending is financed through borrowing instead of taxation. He argued that most of the theoretical literature on the nexus between external debt stock and growth was focused largely on the adverse effect of debt overhang.

2.1.2 Classification of Public Debt

Public debts are classified into two types according to their characteristics. When the public debt literature is analysed, it is classified into three main groups: maturity, sources and voluntariness. Public debts according to maturities refer to debts up to 1 year. In short term borrowing, treasury bills and treasury-guaranteed bonds are used. Medium-term public debts refer to debts ranging from 1 year to 5 years. Long-term public debts refer to debts of more than 5 years. The instrument of long-term borrowing is the government bond. These debts are provided from the capital markets and have a higher interest rate than the interest rate of a short term borrowing. Long term debts are classified as redeemable debts and irredeemable debts:

Public debts according to sources: internal debts and external debts. Internal borrowing refers to a country's borrowing from own national resources. External borrowing refers to the resources provided from a foreign country that is repaid with principal and interest at the end of a certain period. External debt has an increasing effect on national income when it is taken vice versa has a decreasing effect on national income when it is paid. Public debts as a voluntary basis: voluntary debts and obligatory debts. Voluntary debts refer to the debts that are lent to the state by its own will and desire. Obligatory debts refer to the debts which are lent by forcing to take the bonds issued by the government. These debts are applied in times of war, natural disaster or economic

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crises. In itself, it is classified as the debt taken by full compulsion; the debts are taken by the threat of forcing, the debt taken by creating the necessary savings and the liabilities taken by moral coercion (Aybarc, 2020).

Productive and unproductive debts are also available. If the debts are used in construction such as railways, power stations, and irrigation projects which contribute to the productive capacity of the economy, they denote productive debts. In this way, productive debts provide a constant flow of income to the state. The state generally pays the interest and principal debts amount from these projects' revenues. If the projects are used in the area, such as war, famine relief, social services, etc., which do not contribute to the productive capacity of the economy, they denote unproductive debts. The state generally pays the interest and principal debt amounts from taxes; therefore, these debts are a burden to the society.

2.1.5 Concept of Economic Growth

This refers to an increase in a country's physical output over a long period of time (Adams, 2004). A nation's total economic output, known as Gross Domestic Product (GDP), is the total monetary or market value of all the finished goods and services produced within a country's border in a specific period of time (Dairu, 2017). A country is therefore said to have economic growth when the real output of goods and services increases at a faster rate than the growth of her population (Adams, 2004). Economic growth is a process by which a nation's wealth/economy increases over time (Kylon and Krusan, 2001). One of the critical multiplier effects of economic growth is wealth creation with development opportunities. It is an increase in the production of economic goods and services compared from one period of time to another (Katuma, 2001). Economic growth is an increase in what countries produce over time driven by four factors of production, namely land, labour, capital and entrepreneurship (David and Moore, 2015). It is an increase in the value of national output, income and expenditure (Gupta and Gamaliel, 2002). Essentially, the benefits of economic growth of a nation are improved standard of living of citizens, higher real incomes and the ability of the government to devote more resources in the provision of infrastructure like health, education, etc.

Empirical Literature Review

2.3.1 Evidence from other Developing Countries

Serrao (2016) assessed the impact of public debt on economic growth in advanced countries. The study employed an econometric research design as secondary time series data spanning 45 years (1964 – 2009) was collated from twenty advanced countries, including Australia, Austria, Belgium, Canada, Denmark, Spain, Norway, the Netherlands, the U.S.A., the United Kingdom, Sweden, etc. Inferential analysis was adopted, and findings that resulted from the study revealed that there exists a negative relationship between public debt and economic growth in advanced countries. Following these findings, the study advocated for new strategies for public debt management in advanced economies, taking into account their economic and financial performance.

Mwaniki (2016) evaluated the effect of public debt on the GDP in Kenya. The study specifically analysed the effect of external debt on GDP, assessed the impact of advances from commercial banks on GDP, estimated the effect of overdrafts from the Central Bank of Kenya on GDP and evaluated the effects of government securities on GDP. The study employed the OLS regression and causal research design, and secondary data spanning twelve years (2003 – 2015) was gathered. Data amassed in the study were analysed inferentially. Findings revealed that bank loans, external debt and government securities have a significant relationship with the GDP of Kenya. Following these findings, the study recommended that the government should encourage sustainable domestic and external borrowing and utilize funds in productive economic areas.

Muhammad (2017) examined the relationship between public debt and economic growth in the Southeast Asian countries. The quantitative research method was adopted as secondary data spanning ten years (2006 – 2015) were obtained from the World Bank National Account Data and OECD National Account Data. Data gathered in the study were analysed using the VAR analytical technique, Granger causality and other inferential analysis. Findings derived from the study showed that public debt affects the economic growth of a country significantly, especially in the long run.

Mousa and Shawawreh (2017) analysed the impact of debt on the economic growth of Jordan. Specifically, the study investigated the impact of external debt on GDP, assessed the impact of domestic debt on GDP, assessed the impact of debt service

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on GDP and evaluated the impact of public debt on GDP. The quantitative research approach was used as the study considered secondary time series data spanning 15 years (2000 – 2015). The least squares regression model was adopted in analyzing the data. Findings gathered from the study revealed that there is a negative impact of total public debt, especially the external debt, on economic growth. Following these findings, the study suggested that nations should rather depend on the available internal resources than depend on external debt.

Alenjundro and Ileana (2017) examined the impact of government debts on GDP in 16 Latin American economies, including Bolivia, Argentina, Chile, Brazil, Costa Rica, Colombia, the Dominican Republic, Mexico, Honduras, Panama, Nicaragua, Peru, Paraguay, Venezuela and Uruguay, for the period 1960–2015, using the two-stage least squares (2-SLS) technique in the analysis. The variables employed in the analysis included the initial level of GDP, gross government debt as a share of GDP and population growth rate. The results indicated that debt has a positive impact on GDP growth but declines to close to zero beyond public debt-to-GDP ratios (between 64% and 71%). Up to these thresholds, additional debt has a stimulating impact on growth. Panagiotis (2018) empirically investigated the nexus between public debt and the determinants of economic growth, such as private and government consumption, investment, trade openness and population growth in Greece, through the application of unit roots and the ARDL model. The unit root tests indicated mixed integration of order zero and order one among the variables. ARDL results revealed that trade openness had a positive effect on economic growth in the long run. The study also addressed the break effects between government debt and economic growth. The result indicated that the nexus between debt and growth depends on debt breaks. Particularly, debt levels before 2000 and the effect on economic growth diminished rapidly, and the growth impacts became negative.

Said and Yusuf (2018) examined public debt and economic growth in Tanzania. The quantitative research approach was adopted as secondary data spanning forty-five years was collated. Cointegration and the VECM approach were used in analyzing data collected from the study. The VECM estimate showed that there is a negative relationship between public debt and economic growth in Tanzania over the study period. In addition, the Granger causality test revealed that there is no causal relationship between public debt and economic growth. Premised on these findings, the

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study suggested that government and policymakers should stop the accumulation of external debt stock over overtime. External debts should be used only for productive investment of the highest priorities that would help in yielding returns for economic reasons (productive purposes) and not for social or political reasons.

Matandare and Tito (2018) evaluated public debt and economic growth in Zimbabwe. The study employed a quantitative research design. Secondary data spanning thirty-six years (1986 – 2016) were gathered from the World Development Indicators database. Data gathered in the study were analysed inferentially. Findings revealed in the study showed that there exists a negative significant relationship between external debt and economic growth in Zimbabwe. The study also ascertained that exchange rate and inflation were also found to have a negative significant relationship with economic growth in Zimbabwe, and external debt exerted a significant positive relationship with economic growth. Based on these findings, the authors advised that the government should step up efforts to boost sources of revenue to finance her growth plans, as external debt accumulation weighs down economic growth, and suggested the need to diversify the economy is crucial and that the government should develop new sectors which can generate revenue to contribute towards economic growth.

Ndieupa (2018) assessed the effect of public debt on the economic growth of the Central African Economic and Monetary Community (CEMAC). The panel research design was adopted, and panel data spanning sixteen years (2000 – 2016) was amassed from developing countries, namely Gabon, Cameroon, CAR, Chad, Republic of Congo and Equatorial Guinea. The study's data was examined using inferential analysis. Discovered from the study was that public debt has an adverse and statistically significant effect on economic growth. Another study carried out by Kharusi and Ada (2018) revealed a negative and significant influence of external debt on economic growth in Oman. They investigated the relationship between external debt and economic growth in Oman from 1990 to 2015 using the ARDL cointegration approach. From their findings, they recommended a more productive use of external debt to impact economic growth positively.

Mhlaba *et al.* (2019) employed the ARDL method on quarterly data from 2002 to 2016 to examine the long run and short run effects of public debt on economic growth for South Africa. The study modelled GDP as a function of gross and net debts, investment, inflation and terms of trade. The empirical results indicated a significant negative impact

of public debt on economic growth. The study was based on South African data and provided a basis to examine the impact of public debt on economic growth from a Nigerian-specific perspective. Studies carried out by Sansa (2020) on the analysis of public debt on economic growth and poverty in Tanzania between 2000 and 2018 showed a negative and insignificant relationship between public debt and all the study's dependent variables (GDP and poverty). The analysis was done using multiple linear regression models. From the findings, Sansa (2020) concluded that public debt has no impact on economic growth and poverty reduction in Tanzania.

2.3.2 Evidence from Nigeria

Essien *et al.* (2016) employed the vector autoregression Granger causality, impulse response and variance decomposition techniques to determine the relationship between domestic debt, external debt, GDP, lending rates and inflation in Nigeria. The result showed that changes in external debt had an effect on lending rates. The results further showed that external and domestic debt had no significant impact on inflation and output level. The study recommended debt with longer tenure and uniformity of borrowing plans across all tiers of government.

Assessing the impact of public debt on external reserves between 1981 and 2013 in Nigeria, Oduntan, Uzom and Oluweseun (2016) recommended that the government should restructure the negotiation mechanisms so it can enable us get conducive rates and payment plans. The conclusion was done based on the finding of the Johansen cointegration test and fully modified least square techniques. The results showed that public debt and broad money supply have long run positive relationship with external reserves and economic growth.

Sunday, Ngozi, Michael and Ogochukwu (2016) carried out research on the impact of public sector borrowings on interest rates, prices, and output in Nigeria. VAR, Granger causality test, impulse response and variance decomposition of the various innovations were engaged in the analysis of the study. The variables specified in the model of the study include real Gross Domestic Product (RGDP), prime lending rate, external debt, domestic debt and composite consumer price index. The estimation results showed that external debt stock raises the prime lending rate. The estimation results showed that stocks to external debt raise the prime lending rate. The result indicated that external and domestic debts have an insignificant impact on the output and general price level.

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Peter and Ferdinand (2016) studied the nexus between debt burden and development tangle in Nigeria for the period 1980–2014 by employing a unit root test, co-integration test and Granger causality test. RGDP, domestic debt, external debt, domestic debt burden, external debt burden, total debt burden and total GDP/debt ratio were the variables employed in the study. The result of the cointegration indicates evidence of a long run relationship among the variables. The Granger causality results revealed that various debt stocks Granger-cause the growth performance of the Nigerian economy.

Abula and Ben (2016) examined the effect of public debt on economic development in Nigeria from 1986 to 2014. The Johansen co-integration test, ECM and the Granger causality test were utilised in the analysis. The variables employed in the study include GDP, external debt stock, domestic debt stock, external debt service payment and domestic debt service payment. The result showed evidence of a long run relationship among the variables. The results of ECM indicated that external debt servicing and external debt stock have a negative and insignificant impact on economic development in Nigeria, while domestic debt stock has a significant influence on economic development. The results also showed that domestic debt service payments have a negative and significant effect on economic development in Nigeria. Therefore, the study recommended that the government should reduce its external debt stock but should accumulate more domestic debt, as it will contribute significantly to the development of the economy.

Lucky and Godday (2017) empirically examined the nexus between the public debt structure and the growth performance of the Nigerian economy for the period 1990–2015 using simple and multiple regression analyses. The variables used in the analysis include GDP, domestic debt, external debt and total debt. The results of simple regression showed that total public debt has a positive and significant impact on GDP in Nigeria. Therefore, the study recommended that Nigeria should pursue domestic policies as opposed to its external debt counterparts.

Elom-Obed, Odo, Elom and Anoke (2017) empirically analysed the relationship between public debt and economic growth in Nigeria from 1980 to 2015. The study adopted the Vector Error Correction Model (VECM) technique in the data analysis. The variable used in the study includes real Gross Domestic Product (RGDP), foreign debt, domestic debt and domestic private savings. The results of the study indicated that: (i) External debt has a significant negative impact on economic growth within the period

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under study; (ii) domestic debt has a significant negative relationship with economic growth within the study period; and (iii) external debt and domestic debt Granger-cause RGDP, with causality running from external debt and domestic debt to RGDP. The implication of the result is that the negative correlation between debt stocks (external debt and domestic debt) and economic growth, which is contrary to a priori expectation, may be highlighting the misappropriation and wrong application (corrupt practices) of the borrowed funds. Based on findings, the study recommended that (i) the government should reduce external debt, and the ones obtained should be strictly used for purposes intended to ensure a positive effect. (ii) Government should cut down on domestic borrowing and ensure that the already borrowed funds are applied for purposes intended to ensure a positive effect.

Idris and Ahmad (2017) examined the productivity of public debt borrowing and economic growth in the sub-Saharan region. The study employed the auto-regressive distributed lag model (ARDL). Secondary time series data spanning thirty-five years was collated in the study. Econometrics estimation techniques were adopted. The result showed that domestic debt exerted a negative effect on economic growth. Based on the findings, the study suggested that fiscal policy practitioners and other related policy makers should earmark substantial attention to the productive utilization of any internally borrowed funds and ensure that resources are allocated to specific growth-oriented programmes and that adequate capacities for loan repayments are well established.

Favour, Ideniyi, Oge and Charity (2017) assessed public debt and economic growth in Nigeria. Specifically, the study investigated the extent to which foreign debt impacts national output in Nigeria, ascertained if domestic debt significantly impacts national output in Nigeria, and determined the degree of causal relationship existing between explanatory variables and national output in Nigeria. The study adopted the quantitative research method. Secondary time series data spanning forty-five years (1970 – 2015) were amassed in the study from the Central Bank of Nigeria. The result stemming from the study revealed that external debt has a significant negative impact on economic growth within the period under review, domestic debt has a significant negative relationship with economic growth within the period under study and external debt and domestic debt granger cause RGDP in Nigeria with causality running from external debt and domestic debt to RGDP. Premised on the result, the study suggested that government should reduce external debt, and the ones obtained should be

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strictly used for purposes intended to ensure a positive effect, and government should cut down on domestic borrowing and ensure that the already borrowed ones are serviced.

Akhanolu, Babajide, Akinjane, Oladije and Osuma (2018) evaluated the effects of public debt on economic growth in Nigeria. The quantitative research technique was adopted, and secondary data from 1982 to 2017 was gathered. Inferential analyses were conducted, and findings from the study demonstrated that internal debt exerted a positive impact on economic growth, while external debt revealed an inverse relationship with economic growth. Premised on the findings, the study suggested that borrowed funds, particularly external debt, should be minimized.

Eze, Nweke and Atuma (2019) conducted a study on public debts and Nigeria's economic growth spanning thirty-six (36) years between 1981 and 2017. The study adopted an ex-post facto research design. Multiple regression analysis was utilized in the study in which the ARDL model and Chow breakpoint test were used in the analysis. Findings revealed external debt has a negative and significant impact on GDP, while domestic debt has a negative and insignificant effect on GDP. Similarly, government expenditure has a positive and significant impact on GDP, while national savings and the consumer price index have a positive and insignificant effect on GDP. Moreover, the results indicated no evidence of significant structural break between the variables. Thus, the study recommended that government should discontinue the use of external debt in financing budget deficits in the economy but can intensify efforts to stimulate revenue internally through efficient investment and economic diversification. Based on the results still, government should not utilize domestic debts in financing budget deficits; rather, there is a dire need to enhance revenue domestically or reduce its current expenditures in order to effectively finance capital investment projects in Nigeria. Analysis of the impact of public debt on economic growth in Nigeria by Michael, Mbam and Emeka (2019) involved the use of multiple regression analysis, an ARDL autoregressive distributed lag model and a Chow breakpoint test. From the result, external and domestic debt had negative effects on GDP, but only the effect of external debt on GDP was significant. The study recommended that external debt should not be used to finance budget deficits.

Ajayi and Edewusi (2020) examined the effect of public debt on the economic growth of Nigeria. The study looked at the relationship between external debt and domestic debt on economic growth using time series data from 1982 to 2018. The data

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were analysed using descriptive statistics, a unit root test, a Johansen co-integration test and a vector error correction model. Generally, domestic debt and external debt have varying degrees of effect on economic growth. Specifically, the result reveals that there exists a negative relationship in both the short and long run between external debt and economic growth, while domestic debt has a positive effect in the short and long run on the economic growth of Nigeria. The paper concluded that policy makers should ensure proper management of domestic debts; national debts should be invested in the provision of basic amenities and programmes needed to encourage development and social wellbeing.

Onyele and Nwadike (2021) examined the impact of Nigeria's public debt burden on economic growth (1981 – 2019). The total debt-to-GDP ratio was used to measure debt burden, while the debt service cost-to-government revenue ratio was used to determine revenue sufficiency. Reserve sufficiency was also measured. The study reveals that in the long run, debt burden, revenue adequacy, reserve adequacy and exchange rate all have a significant negative impact on economic growth when using the ARDL model. In the short run, changes in income and reserve adequacy have a favourable impact on economic growth, whereas changes in debt burden have a negative impact.

METHOD OF DATA ANALYSIS

3.2 Model Specification

The model of this study is drawn from the Harrod-Domar, two-gap and Solow-Swan growth models. These three growth models identify capital (K), labour (L), saving (S) and foreign capital (F) as the determinants of economic growth (Y). This could be expressed in a simplified functional form as presented by Equation 3.1 as follows:

$$Y = F(K, L, S, F) \quad \text{Equation 3.1}$$

Given that change in capital stock is equal to investment and the assumption that savings is equal to investment, the identified determinant of growth from the three growth models will reduce to investment (change in capital stock (K)), labour (L) and foreign capital (F) as shown by Equation 3.2 as follows

$$Y = F(K, L, F) \quad \text{Equation 3.2}$$

Following the assumptions of the two-gap model about the state of less developed economies such as Nigeria, that domestic saving and foreign capital are not sufficient to stimulate growth, which necessitates domestic and external borrowing to propel growth, the growth function could again be expanded to include external debt (ED) and domestic debt (DD). A key variable in the discussion and debt negotiation is debt servicing. Given that servicing such debt could have an impact on economic growth, debt servicing (DS) is also included in the growth function as represented by Equation 3.3 as follows:

$$Y = F(ED, DD, DS, K, L, F) \quad \text{Equation 3.3}$$

The value of foreign capital inflow and external debt to the domestic economy also depends on foreign exchange rate (ER), hence the growth function of this study becomes

$$Y = F(ED, DD, DS, ER, K, L, F) \quad \text{Equation 3.4}$$

Equation 3.4 could be expressed in an estimable form as shown by Equation 3.5 as follows:

$$Y_t = \beta_0 + \beta_1 ED + \beta_2 DD + \beta_3 DS + \beta_4 ER + \beta_5 K + \beta_6 L + \beta_7 F + t \quad \text{Equation 3.5}$$

A priori Expectation

$$\beta_1 > 0; \beta_2 > 0; \beta_3 < 0; \beta_4 < 0; \beta_5 > 0; \beta_6 > 0; \beta_7 > 0; \beta_8 < 8; \beta_9 < 0$$

A priori expectation is drawn from the core objectives which encapsulate the impact of public debt and economic growth in Nigeria. Four control variables – debt servicing (DS), exchange rate (ER), interest rate (IR) and foreign interest rate (USIR) are expected to be negative because of the depreciation of the naira, inflationary activities in the domestic economy and servicing foreign debt is becoming highly expensive for a developing economy like Nigeria. Equation 3.5 will answer the question of how public debt affects economic growth in Nigeria.

Generally, specifications of this nature are estimated based on the researchers' objective. For some, to avoid the internal correlation between the quadratic terms, a system of Generalized Methods of Moments is used (Ekong, 2021). For others, because they want to determine the point in time where debt is unsustainable, autoregressive

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distributed lag methods are used (Nnah, 2020; Kaur and Mukherjee, 2014). We relied on the analytical part by Nnah (2020) in our analysis since even though some of the variables are endogenous, the ARDL provides unbiased long run estimates simultaneity method of assessing both long run and short run effects of one variable on another (Nnah, 2020; Bentzen and Engsted, 2001).

The model for this study is therefore specified in an ARDL form as shown by Equation 3.10 as follows:

$$Y_t = \beta_0 + \sum_{i=1}^p \beta_1 Y_{t-1} + \sum_{i=0}^{q_1} \beta_2 ED_{t-1} + \sum_{i=0}^{q_2} \beta_3 DD_{t-1} + \sum_{i=0}^{q_3} \beta_4 DS_{t-1} + \sum_{i=0}^{q_4} \beta_5 ER_{t-1} \\ + \sum_{i=0}^{q_5} \beta_6 L_{t-1} + \sum_{i=0}^{q_6} \beta_7 K_{t-1} + \sum_{i=0}^{q_7} \beta_8 F_{t-1} + \beta_9 ED_{t-1} + \beta_{10} DD_{t-1} + \beta_{11} DS_{t-1} \\ + \beta_{12} ER_{t-1} + \beta_{13} L_{t-1} + \beta_{14} K_{t-1} + \beta_{15} F_{t-1} \quad U_t \quad \text{Equation 3.10}$$

Where; Y_t = real GDP (N' Trillion), Y_{t-1} = Lags of real GDP, ED = External Debt (N' Trillion), ED_{t-1} = Lags of external debt, DD = Domestic debt (N' Trillion), DD_{t-1} = Lags of domestic debt, DS = Debt Servicing (N' Trillion), DS_{t-1} = Lags of Debt Servicing, INTR = Interest rate, $INTR_{t-1}$ = Lags of Interest rate, ER = Exchange Rate, ER_{t-1} = Lags of Exchange Rate, K = Capital (proxied by gross capital formation (NTrillion), K_{t-1} = Lags of capital formation, L = Labour (Proxied by Labour Force Participation Rate), L_{t-1} = Lags of labour force participation, F = foreign capital inflow (Proxied by foreign direct investment (\$Billion), U_t = Error Term, $\beta_1 - \beta_{15}$ = Model Coefficients

The data used in this study were gathered from secondary sources. These data were time series data collected using the desk survey approach from central Bank of Nigeria (CBN), the Debt Management Office (DMO), World Bank and IMF Statistical database.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

Trend Analysis of Public Debt Behaviour and Economic Growth in Nigeria

Figure 4.2 presents the trend analysis of gross domestic product (GDP) and public debt in Nigeria from 1982 to 2021. The trend shows that public debt grew generally at a declining rate from 1982 to 1996. For instance, public debt grew retrogressively from 43 percent in 1982 to 11 percent in 1985. It further grew from 49 percent in 1987 to 13 percent in 1991. Public debt also fell from 38 percent in 1992 to a negative (-15 percent) in 1996. Within these periods, GDP growth also adjusts to the dictates of public debt movement. Notably, GDP growth fell from 7 percent in 1982 to 4 percent in 1984 before self-adjustment. From 1985, GDP grew from 5 percent progressively to 23.5 percent in 1989 and further grew to 34 percent in 1992. This movement of debt-growth nexus within the period suggests the debt-growth-led proposition popularly propagated by some quarters (Ndoricimpa, 2020).

Figure 4.2: Trend analysis of GDP growth and total debt in Nigeria (1982 -2021).

Source: Author's research (2021).

Beyond 1996, public debt grew astronomically to nearly 65 percent in 1999. Public debt further moved downward from 1999 to an all-time negative of -91 percent in 2006 (because of debt relief granted by the Paris Club in 2005). Beyond 2006, public debt

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took up a positive trend, with a trough of 8 percent in 2008 and a peak of 27 percent in 2010, culminating with 18 percent value in 2021. In the same vein, GDP growth grew positively from 27 percent in 1993 to 39 percent in 1995 and from 8 percent in 1997 to 23 percent in 2000. It however, grew at a declining rate from 28 percent in 2002 to 13 percent in 2011. Other periods of progressive growth of GDP were witnessed from 2015 to 2019, when GDP grew from 5 percent to nearly 12 percent. This periodic growth progression in GDP may indicate lagged effects of public debt in the growth chain.

5.1 Data Presentation

The results of the preliminary properties of the variables are presented in Table 5.1.

Table 5.1: Descriptive properties of the variables

Variable	GDP	ED	DD	DS	IR	EXC	LAB RATE	IR US	FDI	GFCF
Mean	37016.4	2311.9	3594.8	3.9708	17,3098	114.16	60.0817	6.9971	2.5314	21.1312
Median	8134.1	648.81	1016.9	4.2608	17.5000	111.70	60.2500	6.9200	1.8700	22.0520
Maximum	1735.7	1585.23	1942.56	7.9308	29.8000	401.98	75.6000	18.8700	8.8400	33.0400
Minimum	144.03	2.3312	11.1926	73944	7.7500	0.6052	55.2700	3.2500	0.1900	9.8970
Std. Dev.	498.25	3497.6	5162.09	2.1608	4.6379	106.78	3.4987	3.4698	2.5358	5.4094
Skewness	1.2841	2.3427	1.5365	0.2185	0.2692	0.9524	3.0160	1.1478	1.1566	-0.1769
Kurtosis	3.4475	8.3588	4.2469	1.9085	3.5173	3.3218	13.7382	4.7985	3.1834	2.6998
JarqueBera	11.6104	86.5632	18.7899	2.3615	0.9529	6.3760	259.15	14.5278	9.1982	0.3679
Prob.	0.0030	0.0000	0.0083	0.3071	0.6217	0.0413	0.0000	0.0007	0.0161	0.8319
Observations	41	41	41	41	41	41	41	41	41	41

Source: Author's research (2021).

5.1.1 Descriptive Properties

Table 5.1 presents the descriptive properties of the variables in the study. As shown in Table A1, all variables in the study show evidence of emanating from the cluster population. For instance, all variables were positively skewed except gross fixed capital formation, which was skewed to the left (-0.1769) with the labour rate and external debt perfectly spread. All variables also exhibited acceptable peaks, with debt servicing and

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exchange rate as the most flat. The probability statistics of the Jarque-Bera shows that the variables were all multivariate normal, with gross fixed capital formation (0.83), interest rate (0.62) and debt servicing (0.31) most normally distributed.

5.1.2 Correlation Analysis

Table 5.2 presents the correlation analysis of the variables in the study.

Table 5.2: Correlation of the variables

DD	1									
ED	0.83028	1								
DS	-0.24989	0.06676	1							
IR	-0.19759	-0.11127	0.53185	1						
LAB RATE	-0.39292	-0.24039	-0.04618	-0.28532	1					
IR US	0.59052	-0.44763	-0.02375	-0.27107	0.61343	1				
GDP	0.99219	0.78834	-0.29349	-0.19701	-0.40910	-0.62497	1			
GFCF	0.00128	0.38915	0.31115	0.07295	0.17100	-0.00438	-0.03112	1		
FDI	0.29807	0.01278	-0.31873	-0.00104	-0.25107	-0.57804	0.38823	-0.16208	1	
EXC	0.93756	0.85098	-0.10547	-0.08796	-0.40275	-0.68227	0.93864	0.08391	0.37913	1
	DD	ED	DS	IR	LAB RATE	IR US	GDP	GFCF	FDI	EXC

Source: Author's research (2021).

Table 5.2 shows that the dependent variable (GDP) was positively correlated with key independent variables like external debt (0.788) and domestic debt (0.992) and some control variables like foreign direct investment (0.3882) and exchange rate (0.939). However, debt services and foreign and domestic prices of funds were all negatively correlated with GDP. Other variables in the system exhibited various levels of correlations. For instance, external debt was positively correlated with debt servicing (0.067) and domestic debt (0.803). Domestic debt was negatively correlated with debt service (-0.249). Generally, all variables were variously correlated.

5.2 Unit Root Test

The results of the PP and DF-GLS unit root tests are reported in Table 5.3. The PP test indicates that all variables were non-stationary at levels apart from IR, lab rate and IRF.

Applying the DF-GLS test, all variables were non-stationary at levels apart from GFCF and Lab-rate. This implies that the null hypothesis of non-stationarity for all the variables apart from IR, Lab rate, IRF and GFCF, which were rejected at levels; others were rejected at the first difference of each series. Most importantly, the result shows that we can confidently apply the ADRL methodology to the model.

Table 5.3: Unit root test

Variables	PP Level	Prob	PP 1 st Diff	Prob	DF-GLS Level	Prob	DF-GLS 1 st Diff	Prob
GDP	12.4388	1.0000	-11.1264*	0.0000	-1.3414	0.1919	-7.5457*	0.0000
ED	2.5967	1.0000	-8.0518*	0.0000	0.5169	0.6111	-1.9888***	0.0540
DD	17.8498	1.0000	-10.3551*	0.0000	-1.9276	0.5647	-6.0803*	0.0000
DS	-1.7597	0.3945	-4.3194*	0.0015	-1.8308***	0.0762	-4.1886*	0.0002
EXC	2.9733	1.0000	-3.9332*	0.0043	3.0966	0.0036	-4.0458*	0.0002
FDI	-1.6642	0.4413	-7.2760*	0.0000	-1.4126	0.1661	-7.4375*	0.0000
GFCF	-2.3086	0.1743	-5.2646*	0.0001	-3.1198*	0.0035		
IR	-3.3630**	0.0184			-1.2118	0.4217	-8.9363*	0.0000
LAB RATE	-7.4175*	0.0000			-2.0236**	0.0499		
IRF	-3.9476*	0.0040			-0.0052	0.9959	-2.8819*	0.0005

Note: *, **, *** represent significance at 1%, 5% and 10% respectively.

Source: Author's extraction from *eview12*.

The model structure of public debt and economic growth in Nigeria was also tested. This test helps us to be free of model specification bias. After the model's specification test and report on Table 5.4, it was clear that the appropriate debt-economic growth structure for Nigeria is of log-log form and was adopted for the study. Note: DW test is not a criterion for model selection in this instance. We rely on R2 and the significance of the estimates.

5.3 Public Debt and Economic Growth in Nigeria

First we test the variables to see if there is a relationship between economic growth and public debt in Nigeria as presented in Table 5.5. Stated under the null hypothesis of no level relationship, our calculated result value of 6.4553 greater than both the upper

bound and the lower bound for a sample size under 100, shows that the null hypothesis cannot be accepted under 1 percent level of significance. The implication is that there is a verifiable relationship existing between public debt and economic growth in Nigeria that should be investigated.

Table 5.5: F-bound test

Null Hypothesis: No levels relationship

Test Statistic	Value	Signif.	I(0)	I(1)
Asymptotic: n=1000				
F-statistic	6.455339	10%	2.03	3.13
K	7	5%	2.32	3.5
		2.5%	2.6	3.84
		1%	2.96	4.26
Actual Sample Size	41	Finite Sample: n=41		

Source: Authors, extracted from Eviews 12.

Next, we examine the lag property of the relationship and report the result in Figure 1. In the analysis, over 2187 models were randomly examined. At the end, the lag structured selected was ARDL(1,1,1,0,1,1,1) based on Akaike's information criteria.

Figure 5.1: Lag selection test
Source: Author's extracted from Eviews 12

Table 5.6: Long run equation

Dependent Variable: log(GDP)

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
log(ED)	-0.006487	0.079449	-0.081645	0.9356
log(DD)	0.635310	0.117123	5.424280	0.0000
log(DS)	-0.200216	0.159174	-1.257845	0.2201
log(EXC)	0.390472	0.126066	3.097370	0.0048
log(GFCF)	0.318885	0.222907	1.430574	0.1649
log(FDI)	0.271441	0.093923	2.890025	0.0079
log(LABRATE)	0.158133	1.774535	0.089112	0.9297

Source: Author's extracted from Eviews 12

Therefore, the result of the level relationship in Table 5.6 was reported. The result shows that contrary to theoretical expectations, foreign debt weakens economic growth in Nigeria, even though the strength of weakness is not statistically significant. However, domestic debt grew economic growth in Nigeria during the period. A percentage rise in domestic debt grew economic output by at least 0.64 percent and was statistically significant. Total public debt in Nigeria could thus be positive and nearly (63%) increase to economic growth in Nigeria in the long run. In a related finding, total debt servicing in the country decreased economic growth in Nigeria. A percentage rise in debt servicing in the country dipped economic output by not less than 0.2 percent at any point. Beyond this point, the effect of exchange rate, capital stock, foreign income and labour force all exerted positive influence on economic growth. However, the effect of foreign pressure on economic growth (as seen from exchange rate and foreign income) was more significant statistically. Our result shows that, in the long run, reliance on domestic debt sources possesses more growth potential than external debt sources. The reason for this is not far-fetched. With the current pressure on the global financial system, servicing foreign debt is becoming highly expensive for developing economies like Nigeria. Earlier, Swastika, Ndieupa (2018) had found a similar outcome for some economies in

Central Africa, but it was different from that obtained by Said and Yusuf (2018), who found a negative public debt-economic growth nexus for the Tanzanian economy.

The short run result of the relationship between economic growth and public debt is reported in Table 5.7 as follows.

Table 5.7: Short run results

Dependent Variable: $\Delta \log(\text{GDP})$

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
$\Delta \log(\text{ED})$	-0.047462	0.020397	-2.326940	0.0284
$\Delta \log(\text{DD})$	-0.022272	0.061683	-0.361064	0.7211
$\Delta \log(\text{DS})$	-0.107015	0.014779	-7.240897	0.0000
$\Delta \log(\text{EXC})$	0.158616	0.034236	4.633023	0.0001
$\Delta \log(\text{GFCF})$	0.012834	0.040092	0.320122	0.7515
$\Delta \log(\text{FDI})$	0.046303	0.013151	3.520993	0.0017
$\Delta \log(\text{LABRATE})$	-0.031090	0.152359	-0.204057	0.8400
ECM(-1)*	-0.256818	0.031588	-8.130355	0.0000
R-squared	0.809813			
Adjusted R-squared	0.768210			
F-statistic	19.46511	Durbin-Watson stat		2.352437
Prob(F-statistic)	0.000000			

Source: Author's extracted from Eviews 12.

Table 5.7 shows external debt continues to exert a statistically significant negative impact on economic growth of at least a 0.5 percent point decrease at any single rise in external debt. Domestic debt also continues to exert a dampening negative impact on economic growth, but not statistically significant, though this may be expected. The pressure of foreign debt servicing on economic growth may make domestic debt more appreciative than external debt even when the two exert a similar effect on growth (an increase in external debt servicing reduced external debt and increased domestic debt).

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Overall, a rise in domestic debt dipped output growth by, say, 0.2 percent ultimately. Total short run public debt impact on economic growth could thus be negative (-0.06973). Therefore, a percentage rise in public debt in Nigeria in the short run will generally dip output growth by almost 0.7 percent at an instance. As expected, debt servicing exerted a statistically significant negative impact on economic growth in the short run. A percentage rise in debt servicing in Nigeria dipped economic output by at least 0.11 percent. This experience shows that, within the short run, any debt contract initiated will result in debt servicing dampening the economy more than actual debt. Within the period, other positive economic growth drivers were the stock of capital in the economy, foreign incomes and the economy's exchange rate position at various degrees of strength. Overall, our error correction factor was well-behaved, with the correct sign, indicating that any systemic disequilibrium will be stabilized slightly after a quarter's oscillations in a calendar year. Our result also shows that variations in economic growth over the period was due to public debt variations by over 0.76 percent. There was no incident of autocorrelation, as our DW of 2.4 confirms our position.

To confirm the stability of the result, we obtained the CUSUMs of squares for our analysis and report the result in Figure 5.2. The result shows that our estimates were stable and come from the desired population, as our results operated within the acceptable bandwidth of stability at a 5 percent level of significance.

Figure 5.2: Result of stability test.

Source: Author's extracted from Eviews 12.

Discussion of Findings

In this study, we considered the impact of public debt on the economic growth of Nigeria. Our result showed that there is a positive impact of public debt on economic growth in Nigeria during the study period. A rise in total public debt in Nigeria could raise economic growth by nearly 0.63 per cent in the long term. However, most of the positive impact on public debt economic growth is accounted for by domestic debt sources. A percentage rise in domestic debt grew economic output by at least 0.64 percent and was statistically significant. What eroded most of the positive impact of public debt on growth in Nigeria was major debt servicing repayments. We found that a percentage rise in debt servicing in the country dipped economic output by not less than 0.2 percent at an increase.

The short term impact of public debt on economic growth was similarly negative. Both external debt and domestic debt continued to exert statistically significant negative impact on economic growth. Total short run public debt impact on economic growth could thus be negative (-0.06973). Therefore, a percentage rise in public debt in Nigeria in the short run will generally dip output growth by almost 0.7 percent at an instance. As expected, debt servicing exerted a statistically significant negative impact on economic growth in the short run. A rise in debt servicing in Nigeria dipped economic output by at least 0.11 percent. This experience shows that within the short run, any debt contract initiated will result in debt servicing dampening the economy more than actual debt. We can also argue from this analysis that the public debt-economic growth nexus in Nigeria is a long term thing.

Other positive economic growth drivers were the stock of capital in the economy, foreign incomes and the economy's exchange rate position at various degrees of strength both in the short and long run. A review of the derived estimates showed that our results were not the product of chance. They were evidence-based. Our coefficients test confirms that all our results were stable and hence reliable. Clearly, our result is in tandem with that obtained by Precious (2015) in Swaziland. In her study she found that public debt has significant influence on economic growth.

6.2 Conclusion and recommendations

In this study we examined the issue of public debt and economic growth in Nigeria, relying on the country's data from 1981 to 2021. Several arguments have been put forward regarding the negative effects of excessive public debt on economic growth. Applying autoregressive distributed lag models on annualized country data set, we showed that public debt positively affects economic growth in Nigeria. Total public debt in Nigeria could thus be positive and nearly a 63% increase to economic growth in Nigeria in the long run. Most of the negative effect of public debt on economic growth reveals that debt servicing is still unsustainable in the Nigerian sub-region. Thus, we

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made recommendations bordering on, among other things, effective debt management strategies that merge debt pursued interest with growth-inducing objectives. Specifically, we argued that deliberate policies be put in place to ensure that the accumulation of debt in Nigeria is consistent with the country's growth objectives. Also, the government is encouraged to put in place fiscal reforms that would help improve the management of domestic debt and the acceleration of economic growth. This recommendation is premised on the evidence that the recent trend on debt servicing was detrimental to growth. More generally, we recommend that debt contracts must be done from both sustainability and growth dividends perspectives. The most important factor in any public debt is the sustainability of such debt.

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